
**MILITARY PATRIOTISM IN YOUTH FAMILY AND EDUCATION IN
FORMATION PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF COOPERATION OF
INSTITUTIONS**

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Annotation.

*this article highlights the psychological factors of the cooperation of family and
educational institutions in shaping youth military patriotism, and the following main tasks
in educating youth in the spirit of military patriotism.*

Keywords.

*Cooperation, Society, solid, harmonious, initiative, concept, temperament,
truthfulness.*

Educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotism is a multi - stage, systematic, purposeful and coordinated activity of state bodies, public associations and organizations, aimed at forming a sense of loyalty to the motherland in young people, raising them as individuals capable of fulfilling their civil duty and constitutional obligations, protecting the interests of society and the state. The main goal aimed at educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotism is to show activity in young people in various branches of society, especially in types of civil service associated with the military sphere, to be devoted to constitutional and military duty in a peaceful and military environment, to form in them such important characteristics as high responsibility and responsibility for the fate of

When educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism, the following are defined as the main tasks:

- to educate young people in the spirit of national ideology and loyalty to the Republic of Uzbekistan, its people and its president, deeply instill in their heart and mind that the protection of the Motherland is an honorable and sacred duty;

- to be proud of our ancient history and culture, our national heroes who selflessly fought for the independence and prosperity of our native land, to form a feeling of being worthy of them, to strengthen confidence in the power and potential of our national army;

- the need for physically strong and spiritually mature youth for our national army, the understanding that military service is a sacred duty for every citizen of Uzbekistan, as well as strengthening theoretical and practical skills in this regard;

- formation of skills in young people to approach the political and social processes taking place around us and in the world based on our national interests, ideological immunity to various internal and external threats;

- to educate young people with the skills of adaptation to combat actions, quick and independent decision-making in any complex situations, effective use of modern military equipment; to stand ready to defend the interests of Uzbekistan not only in the military sphere, but in all aspects of life, at every step, to be selfless for the country-to instill in the minds of young people

Since the first years of Uzbekistan's independence, reforms have been carried out in the country in every possible way in connection with all spheres of life. A special place in the harmonious growth of our youth is occupied by the neighborhood, family public organizations and educational institutions. Concern for the future generation is one of the national characteristics inherent in our Ring of striving to bring a healthy, harmonious person to adulthood. In fact, the perfect generation initially arises in the family, grows up to be good or bad people in the family environment. Our First President Was I.Karimov said that in the spiritual and moral education of young people, the family, the parents pay tribute to the decisive place:-the child lives in the atmosphere of the family from the day of birth. Traditions, values, traditions inherent in the family form the child's nobility. above all, children realize, feel the demands of society through the school of family life. The parent has obligations to the child, debts that make their end prosperous. They are: to put a good name, to give in the hands of a good teacher, to expel literacy, to make a learned, professional, to make his head double and homely. The possession of a certain spiritual world by members of an individual family as a person to

elevate family spirituality arises on the basis of the relationship between them. The spiritual qualities of the father and mother in the family the Oriental traditions of marital relations determine the level of humanity and morality. It is important that the spiritual world of the family embodies spiritual values such as mutual respect, appreciation, cooperation, compromise, kindness, compassion, kindness, patience, humanity, nobility, respect for adults, self-esteem for the little ones. The veneration of such values in the family, the observance of which creates such a spiritual atmosphere in the family. This is extremely important in the formation of the soul and mind of the growing generation. On this basis, conditions are created for the full realization of the talent and potential of each family member. As a result, the family takes shape as a place of spirituality. Family education is such a stage in the universal process that the basis for the Enlightenment and life lessons that you will later receive throughout your life, the ground serves as the foundation. Each parent, realizing his duties, is obliged to try to fully adhere to all the characteristics that ensure the family's strength, to understand its tasks and goals. As noted by our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev - in his speech at the IV Congress of the social movement of youth of Kamolot, -today it is becoming more and more widespread in our country. It is necessary that the call to make your own child go deep into the heart of every parent, every citizen, without remaining only a dry slogan, become a practical action. To do this, I think it is time to strengthen this issue, that is, the responsibility and duty of parents to raise children, on a legal basis. Indeed, each parent is considered responsible for the upbringing of their child. Important conditions for the upbringing of our children are the fact that families are built on a strong, spiritually healthy basis, especially since the parents themselves are brought up. Parents are considered the teacher of their child today. Because it is from the family that it begins to interest the child to read books. At present, it is necessary to be able to get knowledge and be interested in reading books in order to protect our children from vices that remove them from any humanity. In raising a child, each parent must live with a sense of their responsibility every minute. Only when there is a healthy environment in the family, a healthy, harmonious person is formed in them in every possible way. Youth education is in particular the role of family spirituality in the upbringing of the future generation, which is physically strong, mentally healthy, has a universal culture, a high level, modern knowledge and profession. It is noteworthy that in the works of our great thinkers on the education of the family, our Bibles give special feedback. The family is the main foundation in the formation of a person as a person, finding his place in life, earning self-esteem

within El yurt. The family is a hearth of upbringing that ensures the continuity of life, keeps our sacred traditions, while directly influencing how future generations will grow into a person.

Conclusion: in conclusion, in the preparation of the military, we can put military education at the highest level in every possible way, up to the command of the knowledge institution, the composition of Professor teachers, the commander, veterans, carrying out large measures in cooperation with parents in the formation of a sense of love for the motherland, love for the chosen profession, peace and tranquility of the people.

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